

Plasmon-enhanced fluorescence biosensors and other bioanalytical technologies

Dario Cattozzo Mor^{1†} Gizem Aktug^{1†} Katharina Schmidt^{2†}, Prasanth Asokan¹, Naoto Asai², Jakub Dostalek^{1,2*}

¹ Laboratory of Biophotonics, FZU-Institute of Physics, Czech Academy of Sciences, Prague 182 21, Czech Republic

² Laboratory for Life Sciences and Technology, Danube Private University, 2700 Wiener Neustadt, Austria

[†] equal contribution

* corresponding author

Abstract

Advances in the plasmon-enhanced fluorescence method and its implementations in optical biosensors and other types of bioanalytical technologies are discussed in this paper. In particular, the focus is given to the results that have been achieved over the last ten years concerning the design and preparation of metallic nanostructures tailored for the amplification of weak fluorescence signals and their utilization in the field of ultrasensitive detection and identification of chemical and biological species. Applications and performance characteristics of plasmon-enhanced fluorescence in the areas of analysis of biomarkers for disease diagnostics, environmental monitoring of harmful compounds, and single molecule analysis are critically reviewed.

Keywords: plasmon-enhanced fluorescence, metal-enhanced fluorescence, plasmonic nanostructure, biosensor, sensor, biomarker analysis, environmental monitoring, single molecule detection

1. Introduction

Metallic nanostructures with tailored plasmonic properties became irreplaceable building blocks that currently serve in numerous bioanalytical fields [1]. The attractive characteristics of metallic nanostructures are related to their ability to resonantly couple light-to-surface plasmon modes, which leads to the enhancement of its strength occurring in the close vicinity to their surface. Such optical resonances were firstly utilized for probing of biomolecules and their interaction in a method referred to as surface plasmon resonance (SPR) biosensor [2], offering the advantage of direct label-free detection and interaction analysis of biomolecules [3]. More recently, metallic nanostructures in the form of colloidal nanoparticles become routinely employed in lateral flow tests [4] and other types of colorimetric assays [5]. When deployed on the surface of solid sensor chips, they also frequently act as extremely efficient substrates for sensitive fingerprinting of molecular analytes by the use of surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS) [6] or surface-enhanced infrared absorption spectroscopy (SEIRA) [7]. Among the plethora of these and other modalities, the area of plasmon-enhanced fluorescence (PEF) emerged through the pioneering works in research groups of Wolfgang Knoll [8] and Joseph Lakowicz [9]. Their PEF works stemmed from advances in SPR biosensor-based methods including the development of biointerfaces for their controlled functionalization with biomolecules. In its various forms, PEF has been referred also as to surface plasmon field-enhanced fluorescence (SPFS), surface plasmon-coupled fluorescence (SPCE), or metal-enhanced fluorescence (MEF) depending on the means of coupling between the confined surface plasmon field and

fluorophore emitters. PEF is a method that takes advantage of fluorophore brightness enhancement (by a factor that can exceed 10^3) if the absorption and emission wavelength bands overlay with the spectrum of surface plasmon modes in so-called plasmonic hotspots – locations where the optical field is tightly plasmonically confined. Such functionality becomes extremely useful for the design of ultrasensitive sensors and biosensors capable of specific detection of minute amounts of chemical and biological species by using fluorophore labels, paving the way to more accurate distinguishing of output optical signal from background.

In the last decade, attention devoted to PEF optical phenomenon gained gradually raising attention of scientific community and advances in its implementation in bioanalytical tools has been addressed by a range of recent excellent reviews addressing the preparation of suitable plasmonic nanostructures [10], mechanisms important to efficiently utilize PEF in sensors and biosensors [11],[12],[13] and more recently focusing on concrete applications [14],[15],[16]. This review aims to build upon these works and provide a multifaceted view into this rapidly progressing field with an overview of aspects important for the design of plasmonic nanostructures and means by which they can be prepared (section 2), followed by a description of plasmon-enhanced fluorescence with an overview of reported enhancement factors in relation to complexity and type of plasmonic structures together with readout optical configurations (section 3). Afterward, are discussed biointerfaces that need to be deployed on the surface of plasmonic nanostructures with a particular focus on the fouling, optimizing the distance between the fluorescent emitters and the metallic surface for specific assay formats (section 4). Then, recent applications where PEF sensors and biosensors are particularly making progress are reviewed: for simplified sensitive detection of molecular species serving for diagnosis of diseases in the biomedical field (section 5) and for potentially on-site analysis of harmful compounds in the field of environmental monitoring (section 6). Finally, emerging implementation of PEF in single molecule detection and interaction analysis are discussed as possible future directions where this type of optics and respective materials can be utilized.

2. Metallic nanostructures supporting surface plasmon resonances

2.1 *Classification of surface plasmon modes*

Surface plasmons originate from collective oscillations of charge density and associated electromagnetic field occurring at surfaces of metals. They can be generated in the form of propagating surface plasmons (PSPs) traveling along thin metallic films or as localized surface plasmons (LSPs) at metallic nanostructures. As illustrated in Figure 1, the properties of such optical modes can be manipulated by the design of metallic structure and one can take advantage of the coupling between individual nanoscopic metallic elements serving as building blocks [17]. For instance, LSPs can be excited on spherical metallic nanoparticles, and for their diameter D much shorter than wavelength λ , they exhibit dipole mode character. Its oscillation moment of charge density is parallel to the vector of the driving electric field with intensity $|E_0|^2$ (see Figure 1a). Positioning this nanoparticle at close proximity to a flat surface of a metallic film, where PSPs can travel (see Figure 1b), yields a geometry sketched in Figure 1c. For a narrow gap d between the flat metal surface and the metallic nanoparticle reaching several nanometers, tightly confined electromagnetic field is formed for an LSP dipole orientation perpendicular to the flat surface [18]. A similar effect can be achieved for the geometry where two metallic nanoparticles are assembled in a dimer configuration (depicted in Figure 1d) when the distance d between them is much shorter than nanoparticle size D and wavelength λ [19].

Another coupling regime between LSPs occurs for longer distances between the metallic nanostructure building blocks when they are arranged in periodic arrays (see Figure 1e). For such geometry,

diffraction-based interaction can lead to the occurrence of lattice LSP modes with decreased radiative losses and thus increased the field intensity enhancement factor $|E/E_0|^2$ [20]. An increasingly rich spectrum of interacting LSP and PSP modes can be orchestrated on geometries with higher complexity that are constituted of different types of metallic nanostructures. Figure 1f shows an example of a commonly used architecture consisting of a thin metallic film that is perforated with arrays of nanoscopic holes (nanohole arrays) and contacted with periodic arrays of metallic nanoparticles at a defined distance d . This structure supports a spectrum of localized LSP and propagating PSP surface plasmon modes that confine the field intensity in the pores, at walls of metallic nanoparticles, in the gap, or at the inner and outer side of metallic film (see Figure 1f) [21].

Figure 1 Examples of geometries that support LSP and PSP modes and their possible coupling.

Optical excitation of surface plasmons is accompanied by spatial confinement of electromagnetic field and respective enhancement of its intensity $|E/E_0|^2$ and local density of optical states (LDOS) [22]. On flat thin metal films, the electromagnetic field intensity of resonantly excited PSPs exponentially decays from the metal interface to the adjacent dielectric and typically probes a distance L_p of about 10^2 nm. Their optical excitation typically provides peak field intensity enhancement $|E/E_0|^2 < 10^2$ (see example in Figure 2a simulated for SPs in the red part of the spectrum on Au surface contacted with water). The excitation of LSPs can lead to stronger field intensity enhancement $|E/E_0|^2 > 10^2$ due to the tighter field confinement and respective shorter probing distances L_p of several to tens of nanometers (see example in Figure 2b for Au disk nanoparticle embedded in water dielectric). As this figure demonstrates, LSP field intensity enhancement can be increased by diffraction coupling on periodic arrays of metallic nanoparticles leading to the occurrence of lattice LSP modes when the refractive index of the medium below and above the structure is similar. The locations on metallic nanostructure where particularly strong surface plasmon-enhanced electromagnetic field intensity occurs are often referred as to plasmonic ‘hotspots’. For very narrow gaps $d < 10$ nm on e.g. metallic nanoparticle dimers, the coupling of LSPs via their near field can provide enhancement of field intensity reaching a factor $> 10^3$, see Figure 2c.

Figure 2 Profile of a surface plasmon field of a) resonantly excited PSPs by Kretschmann configuration on a 50 nm thick gold film in contact with water (refractive index of 1.33) at a wavelength of 633 nm and b) LSPs on arrays of cylindrical nanoparticles with a diameter of $D=140$ nm and height $h=50$ nm in the refractive index asymmetrical (refractive index of substrate and superstrate of 1.45 and 1.33, respectively) and symmetrical geometry (refractive index of substrate and superstrate of 1.34 and 1.33, respectively). c) LSPs supported by spherical Au nanoparticle dimer embedded in dielectric with refractive index $n=1.33$ and diameter D and gap d stated in the graph.

2.2 Preparation of plasmonic nanostructures

A large variety of methods become available for the preparation of metallic nanostructures with geometry designed to support the desired spectrum of surface plasmon modes. Their overview can be found in several excellent recent review papers [23],[10], and below there is provided a set of examples that particularly relate to implementations of PEF biosensors and bioanalytical techniques. The choice of the optimum nanofabrication method is crucial with respect to the target design of plasmonic architecture that should take into account the optical readout configuration, nature of fluorescent emitter, and capping with appropriate biointerface as discussed further in more detail.

Among the ‘top-down’ approaches, high-precision tools such as electron beam lithography (EBL) or focused ion beam milling (FIB) are frequently employed for the preparation of complex structures with (almost) ultimate control on shape. For instance, they have been used for fabricating of PEF ‘antenna-in-a-box’ structure composed of a metallic nanoparticle dimer [24] or zero-mode waveguide in a ‘horn antenna’ format [25]. However, the use of such approaches is typically restricted to research studies and is not suitable for routine bioanalytical applications due to the limited fabrication throughput (dictated by the small area that can be structured) and high operating costs required for these lithographical techniques. For practical sensing applications, an important aspect is the possibility of

scaling up the preparation of metallic nanostructure for their implementation into e.g. disposable sensor chips. Figure 3a shows an example of periodic arrays of metallic nanoparticles prepared by UV-laser interference lithography that was shown to be capable of fabrication structures with tuneable plasmonic properties over a large cm^2 area [26]. In this method, a thin photoresist layer is exposed to a UV light interference pattern, followed by the development step and transfer to a thin metallic film with the use of dry etching [26] or lift-off process [27]. Another widely adopted method for high throughput preparation of well-controlled metallic nanostructures is nanoimprint lithography (UV-NIL). It relies on stamps that allow for repeated transfer of desired nanostructure motifs to a UV-light curable resin. As indicated in Figure 3b, the imprinted topography can be coated with metal films to yield plasmonic diffraction gratings [28], nanohole arrays [29],[30], coupled metallic nanoparticle and nanohole arrays [21], and when combined with lift-off metallic nanoparticle arrays can be prepared [31].

An alternative to 'top-down' approaches represents a set of methods that are referred to as 'bottom-up'. Chemically synthesized colloidal nanoparticles can be capped with chemical moieties enabling their trapping at the interface between immiscible phases, leading to the formation of organized lattices due to interfacial electrostatic interactions, capillarity, and van der Waals forces. The Langmuir–Blodgett (LB) method, a classical representation of this technique, utilizes the liquid–air interface for self-assembly into ordered monolayers. These monolayers are then compressed using an LB trough and transferred onto substrates, fabricating densely packed, extended 2D structures [32],[33]. In another approach, pre-prepared colloidal plasmonic nanoparticles are dispersed in a solvent that is let to evaporate on the substrate under controlled temperature and humidity conditions. During solvent evaporation, capillary forces draw the nanoparticles closer together, facilitating their self-assembly that has been utilized for the fabrication of highly ordered 2D [34] or 3D [33] plasmonic nanostructures (see Figure 3c). In the realm of self-assembly - based nanofabrication techniques, DNA nanotechnology rapidly gains momentum and frequently serves for the preparation of precisely controlled metallic nanoparticle structures [35]. In this method, a long single-stranded DNA scaffold is folded by hybridizing it with a pool of short ssDNA oligonucleotides acting as staples. Specific staple strands can be modified with molecules of interest or serve for accurate docking of colloidal metallic nanoparticles capped with complementary short ssDNA strands (see Figure 3d). This strategy allowed for the preparation of a wide range of geometries assembled from metallic nanoparticles including planet-satellite structures [36], controllable dimer nanoparticle plasmonic nanoantennas [37], or even more complex spiral assemblies [38] and structures that can be actively reconfigured by affinity interaction with ssDNA molecules with a toehold [39].

Figure 3 Examples of the techniques used for the preparation of metallic nanostructures based on a) UV laser interference lithography (adapted from [26]), b) UV nanoimprint lithography (adapted from [28]), c) self-assembly of colloidal metallic nanostructures [34], and b) by selective docking of colloidal metallic nanostructures to DNA origami scaffolds (adapted from [35],[37]).

3. Surface plasmon-enhanced fluorescence

3.1. *Coupling between fluorescent emitters and surface plasmons*

The coupling of fluorescent emitters with the confined electromagnetic field of surface plasmons allows them to efficiently alter their emission characteristics (as schematically shown in Figure 4a) via excitation rate γ_e , radiative emission rate γ_r and non-radiative decay rate γ_{nr} . In general, such surface plasmon-mediated transitions can occur at both absorption λ_{ab} and emission λ_{em} wavelengths of the emitter that can take the form of organic dye molecules, quantum dots [40], upconverting nanocrystals [41], or rare earth chelates [42]. For fluorescent emitters with short Stokes shift that is comparable with a spectral width of SPR band (e.g. most common organic dye emitters), the metallic nanostructure supporting surface plasmons can be simultaneously coupled at both λ_{ab} and λ_{em} . The emitters with wide spectral separation of absorption and emission bands may be engineered to couple only via one of these channels with surface plasmons. Let us note that in common fluorescence spectroscopy-based biosensors and assay readouts, the coupling of emitters with the metallic nanostructure is not close to the conditions explored for the strong coupling regime [43]. Based on the semiclassical picture and excitation rate γ_e that is far from saturation, the radiative emission rate γ_r at λ_{em} contributing to the measured fluorescence signal can be described as proportional to the following product:

$$\gamma_r \sim \left| \vec{E}(\lambda_{ab}) \cdot \vec{\mu}_{ab} \right| \times \eta \times CE(\vec{\mu}_{em}, \lambda_{ab}) \quad (1)$$

where \vec{E} is the electric intensity vector of the excitation light beam, $\vec{\mu}_{ab}$ is the absorption dipole of the fluorescent emitter, η is the emitter quantum yield, and CE states of the collection efficiency of emitted photons at λ_{em} of used optical system. The first term corresponds to the excitation rate γ_r , which can be locally increased by the plasmonic enhancement of the field intensity $|E/E_0|^2$. Importantly, this interaction depends on the orientation of the emitter taken into account by the $\vec{\mu}_{ab}$ vector and there

may be considered whether it is static (e.g. emitters embedded in dense polymer films [44]) or allowed to freely rotate (when e.g. immobilized via flexible polymer chains to the surface [45]). The second term defines the dependence of quantum yield $\eta = \gamma_r / (\gamma_r + \gamma_{nr})$ that can be increased by the surface plasmon-enhanced LDOS (affecting γ_r , particularly for emitters with low inherent quantum yield η_0 [46],[47]) or decreased through the effect of quenching γ_{nr} . The quenching occurs in close proximity to metals due to coupling to lossy surface waves and it is strongly dependent on the distance f of the emitter from the surface. As illustrated in Figure 4b for Au surface in the red part of the spectrum, this effect is pronounced at distances f below about 15 nm, and it is stronger for emission dipole $\vec{\mu}_{em}$ orientation parallel to the surface compared to the perpendicular one. The third term CE describes collection efficiency that can be particularly improved for plasmonic systems, where the emission to the far field occurs via surface plasmons. Directional emission on e.g. tailored diffraction gratings [48], [49], [50] or plasmonic particle assemblies resembling nanoantennas [51], [52],[53] offers means for improved extraction of emitted fluorescence light in optical systems that image the fluorescent object to a detector by using optics with lower numerical aperture.

Figure 4 a) Schematics of the coupling of fluorescent emitters with confined electromagnetic field of surface plasmons at the emitter when employed in sandwich immunoassay and b) distance-dependent changes in quantum yield in the red part of the spectrum for Au surface (adapted from [45]).

3.2 Optical readout systems

The most commonly used optical readout systems in PEF-based assay readout rely on established optical configurations for widefield fluorescence microscopy, confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM), and total internal reflection fluorescence microscopy (TIRF). In widefield fluorescence microscopy selected macroscopic area on the sensor chip is illuminated with the excitation beam at λ_{ex} and the emitted fluorescence at λ_{em} is imaged to a CCD or CMOS-based camera. In most cases, the excitation beam is delivered to the specimen and emission radiation is collected by the same objective using the epi-illumination configuration (see Figure 5a). Another approach relies on scanning the excitation beam at λ_{ex} over the surface by using CLSM and fluorescence light at λ_{em} is detected by a photomultiplier or avalanche photodiode. This setup allows for efficient suppressing of background (particularly through the confocal configuration), but typically provides slower readout. Both widefield and confocal configurations are largely used in the context of microarray scanners deployed in standard molecular biology laboratories [54] (see Figure 5b). CLSM is often used with high numerical aperture objectives for high spatial resolution measurements that requires optical matching to the analyzed substrate to the objective. The wide field imaging can be utilized for examining larger areas with weaker magnifying optics featuring lower numerical aperture imaging system that can e.g. benefit from directional surface plasmon-coupled emission (see term CE in equation (1)).

TIRF relies on the excitation via evanescent waves at λ_{ex} generated upon total internal reflection at the analyzed surface [55]. These waves decay exponentially away from the interface, reaching maximum distances of a few hundreds of nm. This configuration has been utilized for the resonant excitation of PSPs on glass substrates with thin metal film providing enhancement in the electromagnetic field strength in a method referred to as surface plasmon-enhanced fluorescence spectroscopy – SPFS [8]. This method allows for probing short distances of about 100 nm from the metallic surface and was implemented in combination with other bioanalytical tools such as SPR biosensors [56], see Figure 5c. For investigation of more complex biointerfaces and probing larger analytes the utilizing of optical waveguide spectroscopy was reported with the use of evanescent enhanced field intensity penetrating to longer up to micrometer distances [57].

Figure 5 Optical system for PEF utilizing a) confocal microscopy with a structure probing by LSPs (adapted from [25]), b) probing by PSP modes with attenuated total reflection method and Kretschman geometry (adapted from [58]), c) scanning epi-illumination microscopy (adapted from [59]) and d) wide-field microscopy using a smartphone-embedded detector (reproduced with permission from [60]).

Advances in the smartphone-based technologies enabled using devices as detector output units in numerous fluorescence-based analytical systems, particularly useful in point-of-need settings for the detection of cells, bacteria, viruses, and biomarkers. These mobile microscopy devices are pursued to provide cost-effective, field-portable, and easy-to-use alternatives to established benchtop devices deployed in laboratories. Recent developments in smartphone camera technology have improved their performance, approaching that of scientific grade detectors as demonstrated by fluorescence microscopy of DNA origami constructs with predefined numbers of fluorophores to quantify the sensitivity. The sensor exhibited a detection limit of ~ 10 fluorescent dyes per diffraction-limited spot [61]. These types of detectors were tested with simplified microscopy optical systems objective lens showing that in conjunction with PEF providing an average EF of 89 ± 7 single fluorescence emitters are detectable [62]. Other examples include dual-wavelength fluorescent biosensors with smartphone imaging equipped with laser diode modules with collimator lenses (λ_{ex} of 488 and 515 nm), and bandpass filters with wavelengths $\lambda_{em}=520$ and 605 nm [63]. A personalized portable fluorescence microscope was created by embedding a smartphone camera within a 3D- printed housing which includes focusing knob adjustment.

3.3 Comparison of PEF structures and geometries

The overall enhancement factor EF provided by plasmonic nanostructures is often used for comparison of the PEF performance and it can be defined as a ratio of the emitted photon flux delivered to a detector from a fluorophore attached to the amplifying structure compared to that from the same emitter without the structure. In general, it is not a universal characteristic of the metallic nanostructure, but as equation (1) indicates it depends on the characteristics of the emitter (e.g. its quantum yield in the bulk medium η_0) as well as on the optical configuration (affecting the collection efficiency CE) and ability to position the emitters at location probed by the surface plasmon field (plasmonic 'hot spots' where the field intensity enhancement $|E/E_0|^2$ and LDOS peak). This section provides an overview of implementations of PEF illustrating the relation between EF and the metallic nanostructure geometry, the preparation route, and readout configuration. It aims at guiding the reader towards the most suitable options for their intended use and Table 1 presents a set of relevant examples of recent works. As discussed below, certain approaches offer strong EF by precisely controlling the placement of plasmonic nanostructures and fluorophores but rely on techniques that are complicated for scaled-up preparation. Some techniques allow for probing of very small detection volumes, making them more suitable for single-molecule detection, while others are better suited for sensors probing larger surface areas that are established for routine readout of assays in the analysis of molecular ensembles.

Table 1 Examples of metallic nanostructures designed for plasmon-enhanced fluorescence illustrating the relation between enhancement factor EF , employed fabrication technique for metallic nanoparticle (NP) preparation, optical readout configuration, and used fluorophore.

Plasmonic structure	EF	Fabrication technique	Readout geometry	Fluorophore	Ref.
<u>DNA origami with metallic colloidal NP</u>					
Au nanorod NP dimer	1.1- 1.7×10^3	DNA origami, gap of 12 nm	Inverted confocal fluorescence microscope	Cy7, ATTO740, Alexa Fluor 750	[64]
Au spherical NP dimer	5×10^3	DNA origami, gap of 12-17 nm	Inverted confocal fluorescence microscope	ATTO647N	[37]
Ag spherical NP dimer	4.5×10^2	DNA origami, gap of 12 nm	Wide field fluorescence microscope with smartphone detector	ATTO647N	[62]
<u>Metallic colloidal NP</u>					
Ag nanocubes NP on Au surface	1.5×10^2	Chemical synthesis of NP	Confocal fluorescence microarray scanner	Alexa647	[54]

Au spherical NP dimers	6×10^2	Aggregation of chemically synthesized NPs	Inverted confocal fluorescence microscope	Alexa Fluor 647 with quencher	[65]
Subdiffractive Au NP arrays	4.5 - 70×10^3	Self-assembly, block copolymer micelle nanolithography	Wide field inverted fluorescence microscope	Cy5	[66], [67]
<u>Lithography</u>					
Au multi-period plasmonic grating	3×10^2	UV-LIL/UV-NIL	Wide field epi-illumination microscope	Alexa Fluor 790	[28]
Au Nanohole/Disk Arrays	10^2	EBL/UV-NIL	Attenuated total internal reflection	Alexa Fluor 647	[49]
Au antenna in a box	1.6×10^3	EBL	Inverted confocal fluorescence microscope	Alexa Fluor 647 with quencher	[24]
Au nanohole/disk arrays	$3-4 \times 10^2$	Nanosphere lithography with Ar milling	Fluorescence spectrometer with right-angle configuration	Alexa Fluor 790	[68]

One of the largest EF is obtained in a narrow gap between metallic nanostructures. It can be utilized from metallic nanoparticles forming a dimer configuration (see Figure 1d) with fluorophores placed in a nanoscale gap of $d \sim 10$ nm. Such geometry supports tightly confined LSP field intensity that is enhanced by a factor rapidly increasing when closing the gap distance d (see Figure 2c). In one route, such geometry was lithographically prepared by EBL combined with template stripping in order to yield flat arrays of nanoantennas [24]. It was composed of a dimer of 80-nm inverted Au half-spheres with 10 nm nanogap optimized for single-molecule analysis in a detection volume of approx. 20 zL. This approach was reported to allow reaching $EF = 1600$ for quenched Alexa Fluor 647 fluorophores. In order to simplify the preparation route, aggregation of colloidal gold nanoparticles into dimers or trimers was reported by using drop-casting for PEF studies [65]. The tuning of the gap was facilitated by capping the chemically synthesized nanoparticles with a sacrificial polyethylene glycol spacer. For a gap size close to 6 nm there was achieved EF of 600 for the same quenched Alexa Fluor 647 fluorophore.

In another route, precisely controlling of nanogaps between plasmonic nanoparticle dimers where fluorophores can be precisely positioned has been explored by using DNA origami constructs [69]. In this approach, self-assembled, three-dimensional DNA origami scaffolds are shaped in the form of a pillar and present specific docking sites for two colloidal metallic nanoparticles, with a cleared hotspot for the incorporation of a fluorophore (see Figure 3d). For instance, by using Au nanorods with dimensions 67 nm by 20 nm anchored to the DNA pillar forming a 12 nm dimer gap, there was a

reported enhancement factor of $EF = 1600$ for Cy7 fluorophores, $EF = 1400$ for ATTO740, and $EF = 1100$ for Alexa Fluor 750 [64]. The obtained antennas presented a narrow dispersion in dimer gap dimensions (average 11.7 ± 2.7 nm), showing the reproducibility of the proposed self-assembly technique and assuring strong field enhancement at the fluorophore location. On the other hand, when compared to the lithographic fabrication technique of the previous example, this work reported a larger deviation in the antenna geometry (angle between the longitudinal axes of the Au nanorods of $134 \pm 33.8^\circ$) leading to increased variation in the plasmon resonance wavelength for each antenna (varying between 650 and 910 nm). Similar DNA origami geometry was proposed in earlier works, but with the use of gold nanospheres instead of nanorods [37],[70]. The reported fluorescence EF was lower (EF approx. 500) than more recent works, due to the intrinsic stronger enhancement given by the nanorod sharper curvature. Both classes of PEF structures were used for confocal microscopy – based studies to probe individual antennas, making the read-out suitable for specialized optical laboratories.

Colloidal metallic nanoparticles also served as building blocks in other geometries explored for PEF substrates with the possibility of structuring larger surface areas. Block copolymer micelle nanolithography was developed for the self-assembly of closely packed hexagonal periodic arrays of spherical Au nanoparticles. This technique allowed to yield of a hexagonal lattice of Au nanoparticles with a diameter D of 50 nm arranged with a narrow gap d of about 20 nm. For PEF substrates prepared by such a potentially scalable fabrication method, extraordinarily high $EF > 10^4$ was reported for Cy5 emitter [66] with wide-field fluorescence microscope. The same research group expanded the earlier work by making the plasmonic substrate dual-resonant for coupling the LSPR wavelength with the emission/excitation peaks of Cy5 and 5-FAM, while preserving high enhancement factors reaching $EF = 4.5 \times 10^3$ and 1.6×10^2 for Cy5 and 5-FAM, respectively [67]. In another approach, $EF = 1.5 \times 10^2$ was obtained by a sandwich immunoassay with colloidally-synthesized silver nanocubes [54]. The Ag nanocubes were conjugated with an antibody and allow for fluorescence enhancement in the cavity when, in the presence of the antigen, a 20-nm gap is created between the Ag nanostructure and flat gold surface bearing another antibody recognizing the antigen.

In addition to nanostructures supporting the tightly confined electromagnetic field of LSPs, metallic thin films with PSPs traveling over the interface allow for enhancing the fluorescence signal intensity of attached emitters. For flat Au thin films, PEF is often combined with SPR sensors in Kretschmann configuration for resonant excitation of PSPs, providing enhancement factors $EF < 10^2$ [71]. The structuring of such thin metallic films allows for increasing the enhancement factor EF to about 10^2 by e.g. perforating arrays of nanoholes in it (see geometry in Figure 1f), obtained from a master structure (fabricated by EBL) with the use of UV-NIL [49]. Periodically corrugated thin metallic films allow also for diffraction-based coupling to PSPs and multi-periodic plasmonic gratings prepared by either UV-LIL/UV-NIL [28] or nanosphere lithography [68] were explored for PEF. A structure featuring overlaying periodicities (see Figure 3b) was designed for simultaneous excitation of SPP modes at two spectral bands overlaying with the fluorophore (Alexa Fluor 790) excitation and emission spectra. By combining enhancement of the excitation rate and directional surface plasmon-coupled emission, the structure allowed reaching EF of $\sim 3 \times 10^2$, with the use of wide-field fluorescence microscopy in epi-illumination configuration.

4. Biointerfaces and assay formats

Dedicated biointerfaces have been devised for surfaces of metallic nanostructures enabling optical probing of the sensor surface with the confined electromagnetic field of surface plasmons. These

typically polymer-based surface architectures are designed to provide a) controlled docking of biorecognition elements (BREs) that facilitate a specific capture of target species from analyzed liquid samples at the sensor surface and b) preventing sensor surface blocking due to the adsorption of other abundant molecules present in analyzed sample. The anchoring of BREs is typically allowed by the incorporation of chemical handles to the biointerface enabling their conjugation via amine [72] or thiol groups or by using tags such as biotin or azide. The ability of repelling of fouling was pursued by using a vast range of polymer architectures and the development of such biointerfaces has been subject to numerous recent reviews [73]. This section is dedicated to several important aspects that are particularly relevant to PEF bioanalytical technologies including a) approaches for selective functionalization of the surface of metallic nanostructures at areas, where the electromagnetic field intensity is confined – so-called plasmonic hotspots and b) at systems that allow for combining antifouling properties with controlling distance of captured molecules from the metal surface at nanoscale, which is important for the majority of PEF assay formats.

4.1 Selective functionalization of plasmonic hotspots

In order to fully harness the potential of PEF, the respective structure needs to assure that the assay readout takes place at the location, where the electromagnetic field is confined by the resonant coupling to surface plasmons. As discussed in the section 3, this typically occurs at spatially confined volume in the vicinity to metallic nanostructures referred to as plasmonic hotspots. This section provides an overview of techniques that were recently explored for the precise attachment of biomolecular species at metallic nanostructures that can be employed for docking of BREs with nanoscale accuracy.

UV laser interference lithography was employed for aligning of photo-activated attachment of a hydrogel binding matrix with periodic arrays of Au nanoparticles [74]. It employed simultaneous attachment and crosslinking of pNIPAAm-based polymer with carboxylic groups that were used for subsequent conjugation of immunoglobulin G (IgG) molecules to the responsive hydrogel wrapping over the metallic nanostructure, see Figure 6a. Similar pNIPAAm-based material was combined with a substrate carrying quasiperiodic plasmonic nanopores in order to serve as actively controllable gates [75]. These responsive polymer gates were demonstrated to allow for on-demand trapping and release of biomolecules in the nanopores that were probed with the confined field of LSP supported by this nanostructure, Figure 6b. The orthogonal linker chemistry approach was implemented for the selective coupling of protein molecules at a gap between lithographically made metallic nanoparticles forming a plasmonic hotspot [76]. Arrays of Au nanorod dimers were prepared by EBL on a SiO₂ substrate with a TiO₂ material deposited in the gap. Then, passivating of the Au surface with thiol-PEG molecules was followed by the selective reaction of dopamine-biotin molecule at the TiO₂ pad and by backfilling the SiO₂ surface with poly-lysine-PEG. The yielded structure was then proposed for selective binding of streptavidin at the plasmonic hotspot that overlaps with TiO₂ pads. Plasmon-enhanced photochemistry represents another route that was explored for selective functionalization of metallic nanostructure with plasmonic hotspots. Au nanoparticle assemblies were utilized for plasmonically-assisted ejection of hot electrons at the hotspot that selectively desorb thiol self-assembled monolayer (SAM) from the nanostructure [77]. As illustrated in Figure 6c, the deprotected area can be afterwards backfilled with functional thiol molecules including ssDNA-thiol or thiol-biotin for selective coupling of ssDNA with a fluorophore reporter or streptavidin. In a similar direction, the plasmonically generated hot electrons were employed for local triggering of polymerization at the plasmonic hotspots as seen in Figure 6d, [78]. In conjunction with synthesizing polymers bearing functional units, this approach can provide an efficient means for selective docking of BREs at the plasmonic hotspot. An increasingly popular approach to the preparation of complex plasmonic nanostructures with the ability to accurately place

biomolecules in plasmonic hotspot is based on DNA origami [60]. This technology has been implemented for the self-assembly of plasmonic nanoantennas from synthetically prepared metallic nanostructures and ssDNA staples that can be engineered to carry functional units at the desired location where the plasmonic hotspot occurs. As Figure 6e illustrates, these units can be prepared in the form of ssDNA that allows for specific binding of complementary ssDNA strands.

Figure 6 Examples of explored routes for the selective functionalization of metallic nanostructures based on a) photo-attachment with interference UV field pattern overlaying gold nanoparticle arrays (reproduced with permission from [74]), b) actuating of plasmonic nanopores for diffusing biomolecules with grafted from responsive pNIPAAm-based brushes (reproduced with permission from [75]), c) using of locally ejected hot electrons for deprotecting selected areas (reproduced from [76]). d) Plasmon-enhanced photochemistry (reproduced with permission from [77]), and e) DNA origami scaffolds (reproduced with permission from [60]).

4.2 Repelling of fouling and control of the distance from the metallic surface

As introduced in section 3, emitters serving as reporting molecules for the PEF readout need to be placed at an optimum distance f from the metal surface in order to reach the maximum enhancement factor EF . This constraint needs to be taken into account when designing the biointerface of metallic nanostructures and besides the accurate distance control it has to provide means to immobilize sufficient amounts of BREs and sustain the ability to repel other molecules present in the liquid sample. This part focuses on a subset of polymer-based biointerface architectures which reflects these three requirements.

For probing with localized surface plasmons - LSPs, the enhanced electromagnetic field intensity occurs at a distance range comparable to the size of the biomolecules, i.e. at the order of 10^0 nm (for instance, see the gap size of 11 nm showed in Figure 6e for the plasmonic nanoparticle dimers). This leads to the requirement of using very thin linker layers for the immobilization of BREs. Most commonly, such linker layers are prepared by self-assembly of thiol molecules. Such SAMs exhibit a thickness of several nanometers and thiols with polyethylene glycol (PEG) become established widely used materials for repelling protein sorption. Thiol with carboxyl or biotin headgroups is often used for coupling of BREs in combination with thiol-PEG. It is worth noting that other chemical toolkits for thiol SAMs have been recently developed with alternative headgroups such as zwitterionic carboxybetaine and sulfobetaine units [79] (see Figure 7a) that have been frequently used in more advanced antifouling materials [80].

The class of biointerfaces relying on the polymer brush architecture was shown to offer improved antifouling properties in plasmonic biosensors compared to thiol SAMs [81]. These coatings can act as efficient three-dimensional matrices with a thickness of several tens of nanometers and therefore they are suitable for PEF formats relying on the probing of propagating surface plasmons – PSPs exhibiting more extended profile of electromagnetic field (see Figure 2a). The utilization of PEF for the detection of biomolecules present in complex samples such as saliva was reported with the use of poly[(N-(2-hydroxypropyl) methacrylamide)-co-(carboxybetaine methacrylamide)] copolymer brush that was grafted from the gold surface forming a layer with the thickness 81 nm in the swollen state [58] (see Figure 7b). Interesting types of antifouling polymer binding matrices are prepared from responsive crosslinked polymer networks [82]. These networks can take the form of thin hydrogel layers attached to the metallic sensor surface and they can be toggled between swollen and collapsed states. Arguably, the most prominent responsive polymer is poly(Nisopropylacrylamide) (pNIPAAm) and it exhibits attractive thermoresponsive properties due to its local critical solution temperature (LCST) at around 32 °C. Its copolymers were synthesized for the preparation of three-dimensional binding matrixes with thickness extended $> 10^2$ nm in the swollen state [83] that is far above the probing depth of surface plasmon waves. However, by triggering the collapse of the polymer network by increasing the temperature about the LCST, affinity-captured molecules can be compressed at the metallic surface and thus open the door for increased efficiency of PEF readout through compacting them at the optimum distance [74], see Figure 7c. Importantly, The magnitude of the collapse in the pNIPAAm-based binding matrix depends on the surface mass density of BREs, and therefore using low molecular weight BREs such as short peptides offers the advantage in this concept [84].

Figure 7 Examples of routes for functionalization with controlled distance of affinity captured target molecules from the metallic sensor surface by using a) several nanometers thick thiol self-assembled monolayers (reproduced with permission from [79]), b) several tens of nanometers thick biofunctional antifouling polymer brushes (reproduced with permission from [58]), and c) and responsive polymer networks postmodified with biofunctional moieties featuring actuated thickness d_h that can exceed 100 nm (reproduced with permission from [84]).

4.3 Assay formats and cyclic reaction amplifications

In PEF affinity-based biosensors, BREs such as antibodies, aptamers, and peptides are anchored at the surface of metallic structures to specifically interact with the target analyte in analyzed liquid solution. Target analytes are typically not fluorescent themselves and therefore the BREs need to be labelled with fluorophore tags. When interacting with the target analyte, a plasmonically enhanced fluorescence signal can be generated by several means. A direct assay format is possible by using BREs that upon the capture of the target analyte change their conformation [85],[86]. In addition, there are commonly used direct [87], [88] and indirect [89], [90], [88] sandwich or indirect [91],[92] and competitive [72] formats that rely on more assay steps.

In immunoassays, antibodies are used as BREs and a sandwich format is frequently used [72], [93]. A capture antibody is immobilized on the sensor surface to affinity bind the target molecule from the contacted liquid sample. Afterwards, the fluorophore-labeled detection antibody is attached to another part of the captured analyte and the measured fluorescence signal is proportional to the analyte concentration. The most frequently used detection technique in PEF platforms is indirect sandwich immunoassay, which has a capture antibody on the substrate, a detection antibody to detect the target analyte, and a fluorophore-tagged secondary antibody providing the signal [94]. The advantage is that using tagged secondary antibodies instead of directly tagging detection antibodies (as done in a direct sandwich assay) can offer simplification in multiplexed formats. The other prevalent approaches utilize aptamers [95], single-stranded DNA (ssDNA) [96], or RNA (ssRNA) [97], instead of antibodies as recognition elements.

Additionally, nucleic acids designed to form a hairpin structure with a fluorophore on one end and a quencher at the other end of the strand, so-called molecular beacons (MBs), were commonly employed in PEF systems [85], [86]. In the closed state of the hairpin, the system is turned “off”, when the fluorophore is in proximity to the quencher, while in the “on” state, fluorescence is emitted upon binding of the analyte leading to the opening of the hairpin structure and gaining enough distance to the quencher. Such an approach has been implemented by using a hairpin aptamer BRE. [45] The readout of the assay was based on the measurement of affinity interaction – modulated fluorescence quenching of the attached fluorophore that is strongly dependent on the distance from the metal (see Figure 4).

When employed for the readout of fluorescence assays serving for sensitive detection of chemical and biological species, PEF can be combined with other strategies further improving the sensitivity. Enzyme-based and enzymatic-free approaches were investigated in order to complement optical PEF amplification (that increases the brightness of the fluorophore labels) by associating the capture of the target analyte with an increased number of fluorophore labels. Rolling circle amplification (RCA) was employed in combination with PEF for the analysis of DNA and protein analytes. In this method, a short ssDNA tag is used and hybridized to a circular ssDNA called a padlock probe. This short oligo tag, serving as a primer, can be extended upon binding of the polymerase enzyme and the addition of nucleotides. Long ssDNA strands with the repeating sequences complementary to the padlock are synthesized and they can serve for docking of multiple fluorophores [71]. Another approach for signal amplification is the implementation of cyclic fluorescence probe cleavage, in which the DNA strand is cleaved by an endonuclease to thermo-plasmonically release the fluorescent probes regenerating the target analyte on the surface [98].

In order to simplify the amplification schemes and make them more robust, efforts were devoted to the development of enzyme-free approaches and catalytic hairpin assembly (CHA) is a prominent approach in this research direction. DNA hairpins are designed to open by strand displacement when a trigger is introduced, forming a complex. When the first hairpin is open, it discloses an ssDNA sequence serving as a toehold capable of reacting with a second hairpin leading to releasing the initial

trigger sequence, which can then be used for the next reaction cycle. Such reactions were frequently proposed for replacing enzyme-based RCA [99]. It was shown that in combination with PEF CHA allows for single molecule detection [100]. This technique was advanced to form dendrimers, branched structures, and DNA walkers [101], [102]. There was reported a similar approach in combination with DNAzymes for cleavage of strands to prepare the gold nanoparticles that initiate the CHA engineered to take place at DNA tetrahedrons [103]. The CHA was also used in PEF-based read-outs for precise imaging in vitro and in vivo [104].

5. Applications in disease diagnostics

Sensitive analysis of biomarkers and harmful biological compounds holds great potential to serve for early disease diagnosis enabling early guiding respective treatment as well as allowing for disease relapse monitoring. However, efficient detection of such biological targets remains challenging due to their low quantity and presence in complex biological samples. To detect the targets that are often present at concentrations in the pM-fM range or below, PEF-based platforms have been demonstrated as ubiquitous tools enabling improving the limit of detection (LOD) of developed fluorescence assays. In this chapter, we aim to present the recent PEF-based biosensing studies and illustrate the variety of developed signal-enhancing plasmonic nanostructures and biorecognition mechanisms that are able to detect minute amounts of analytes associated with a wide spectrum of diseases, including cancer, parasitic, viral, and bacterial infections, and neurodegenerative diseases. As discussed further, the reported PEF-based biosensors for biomarker detection can be categorized into two main groups utilizing a) plasmonic nanostructures attached to the surface of solid sensor chips and b) solution phase-based sensing platforms where plasmonic colloidal nanoparticles are exploited.

5.1 Cancer biomarker analysis

PEF-based biosensing platforms have been widely explored for the detection of biomarkers related to numerous types of cancers, see Table 2. Early detection of cancers is of paramount importance since it is the main cause of death worldwide. In the context of liquid biopsy, there are pursued tools that can provide require ultralow LOD in conjunction with non-invasive means of sampling of bodily fluids (e.g. blood serum or plasma) in which the target biomarkers circulate.

Exosomal miRNAs (exomiRs) are regarded as a potentially rich reservoir of biomarkers for early-stage cancer diagnosis, and they can be simply obtained from serum or urine. For this purpose, the Au nanorods (AuNRs) were drop-casted on Ag-island film, and the capture antibody was attached to the surface via amine coupling [89]. Such substrate was used to identify the exosome membrane marker, CD63, in an indirect sandwich immunoassay (Figure 8a) with AF647-tagged secondary antibody and microarray scanner readout. This work reported on 360-fold fluorescence enhancement compared to the glass substrate and the detection limit of 0.3 ng/mL. When the immunocomplex was injected into the plasma samples collected from patients with liver cirrhosis, and hepatocellular carcinoma, and two healthy donors, increased secretion of exosomes allowed for the distinction of cancer patients from the healthy controls.

Besides exomiRs, cell-free miRNAs circulating in bodily fluids or the miRNAs that can be obtained from cell lysates are also recognized as biomarkers for the diagnosis of cancers at early stages. miRNA-210 and miRNA-21 have been found to be up-regulated in several kinds of cancer including colorectal and breast cancer [105], [106], [107]. Their analysis was reported by using flower-like silver (FLS)-enhanced fluorescence/visual bimodal readout with increased sensitivity and multiplexed format [108]. The FLS layer was grown on the surfaces of cellulose fibers, and then nitrogen-doped carbon nanodot-

functionalized DNA1 (DNA1-N-CDs) was physically absorbed into FLS- μ PADs. DNA2-CeO₂ was added as a fluorescence quencher after the hybridization of DNA1 and DNA2. When the miRNAs were present in the cell lysates, DNA2 bearing the quencher hybridized with the miRNAs leading to the fluorescence recovery. The advantage is the surface can be regenerated and used up to three times after rehybridization of DNA1-N-CDs and DNA2-CeO₂. The LODs were 0.03 fM and 0.06 fM for miRNA-210 and miRNA-21, respectively.

In order to detect miRNA-21 which is overexpressed in numerous types of cancers, a nanogap antenna was fabricated as a highly sensitive sensing element by using two AuNR-conjugated hairpins H1 and H2 [109]. The presence of the target - breast cancer-associated miRNA-21 triggers the Cy5-labelled H1 to unfold due to the hybridization with miRNA-21, leading to fluorescence enhancement, and followed by the dimerization of two hairpin structures, see Figure 8b. In the presence of dNTPs and the polymerase, miRNA-21 is then displaced to catalyze the next reaction and the hairpin structures are elongated, and the fluorescent signal is further amplified by the two AuNR dimers. With this technique, an ultralow LOD of 97.2 aM was reached. For detecting the same miRNA, AuNPs-magnetic beads (MBs) were prepared by adsorbing the negatively charged AuNPs onto the aminated positively charged surface through electrostatic interactions, and single stranded RNA (ssRNA) complementary to the target was immobilized onto the Au surface [110]. Additionally, a fluorescent dye (DTDI)-tagged albumin was conjugated to a viral protein, p19, which possesses the ability to recognize double-stranded RNA (dsRNA). In the presence of miRNA-21 in human serum and MCF-7 cell lysates, hybridization with the complementary ssRNA sequence occurs and the p19 protein binds the formed dsRNA (Figure 8c). This magnetic fluorescence miRNA sensing strategy yielded a broad detection range from 10 fM to 10 nM, with a detection limit of 9 fM. A similar detection strategy was utilized with varying lengths of DNA sequences as a biological spacer to precisely regulate the distance between NIR Ag₂S QDs and AuNRs for the detection of prostate cancer marker PCA3 sequence [111]. Both QDs and the AuNRs were modified by ssDNA chains (DNA1 and DNA2) with sequences designed to simultaneously hybridize with the PCA3 DNA sequence, facilitating the signal enhancement (Figure 8d). The sensor was able to detect the biomarker in human serum samples, and the cell lysates of prostate cancer cell lines PC-3 and LNCap with an LOD of 1.42 pM

Figure 8 Schematic illustrations of PEF-based cancer biosensing platforms detecting a) exosomes in plasma samples by targeting exosomal membrane marker CD63 in an indirect sandwich assay performed on AuNRs drop-casted on Ag island film (reproduced with permission from [89]), b) miRNA-21 detection by DNA/miRNA hybridization and fluorescent signal enhancement by the AuNR nanogap antennas (reproduced with permission from [109]), c) AuNP-magnetic beads and fluorescent-tagged albumin conjugated to p19 for the detection of miRNA-21 [110], d) PCA3 detection by using NIR-tagged QDs and AuNRs (reproduced with permission from [111]).

Carbohydrate antigen 19-9 (CA 19-9) is a biomarker associated with pancreatic cancer. It is one of the most aggressive and lethal cancer types and to increase the very low chance of survival, this disease needs to be diagnosed at a very early stage. To this end, a highly sensitive near-infrared fluorescence immunoassay was developed by using a sensor chip with Au triangular nanoparticle arrays prepared by colloidal lithography technique followed by functionalizing with anti-CA 19-9 monoclonal antibodies [90]. The indirect sandwich assay (see Figure 9a) with a DyLight 800-conjugated secondary antibody allowed reaching an LOD of 7.7×10^{-7} U/mL in serum samples.

By using CRISPR-Cas12a providing a unique trans-cleavage effect, a sensitive and rapid sensor was developed to detect a cell-free DNA (cfDNA) that is related to breast cancer. First, an overhanging DNA bridge was established between the 20 and 60 nm-sized AuNPs [112]. While the double-stranded end was conjugated to the 20 nm AuNP, the single-stranded part, which is recognized by CRISPR-Cas12a, was attached to the 60 nm AuNP (Figure 9b). The shorter sequence of the overhanging DNA is tagged with FITC, at a distance of 2 nm and 7 nm from 60 nm and 20 nm AuNP, respectively. In the presence of breast cancer biomarker - the BRCA-1 gene - CRISPR-Cas12a complex was activated by the hybridization of the BRCA-1 gene with the complementary CRISPR RNA (crRNA) and to cut specifically the ssDNA. This annihilated the fluorescence quenching effect of 60 nm AuNP while unveiling the PEF effect of 20 nm AuNP. It was reported that the detection limit of the system could reach down to 0.34 fM. This approach overcomes the need for pre-amplification-based approaches which are costly and time-consuming.

Caspases are proteolytic enzymes that play a critical role in homeostasis and apoptosis. Dysregulation of caspases can be attributed to several severe diseases including cancer, inflammatory disorders, and

neurodegenerative disorders [113]. Among these, caspase-3 is the central regulatory protein, and its detection was reported by bifunctional AuNPs conjugated with fluorescein isothiocyanate (FITC) via two strands - ssDNA and a peptide [114]. These double bridges were utilized for rapid and sensitive detection of the target analyte by using a peptide sequence than the ssDNA to keep the fluorophore quenched in close proximity ($f < 2$ nm) to the Au NP (Figure 9c). Once the caspase-3 is present in the sample, it degrades the peptide resulting in an increase in the fluorescence signal due to the elevated distance f to 7-8 nm where PEF dominates over the quenching. The LOD of the system was at the caspase 3 concentration of 10 pg/mL.

Epidermal growth factor receptors affect cancer malignancy since they are often overexpressed in various cancer types. The ERBB2 gene codes for a transmembrane protein of this receptor family and it can be targeted as a biomarker molecule. MB probes were immobilized on a nanoporous Au disk, producing a fluorescence signal upon hybridization to the targeted complementary sequence. The sensor was able to detect as low as 2.4 zeptomoles of DNA [86].

Figure 9 Schematics of PEF platforms for the detection of a) pancreatic cancer biomarker CA19-9 in an indirect sandwich assay by using Au nanotriangular array on glass [90], b) cell-free DNA (cfDNA) by activating CRISPR-Cas-12a and AuNPs functionalized with DNA [112], c) caspase-3 by using AuNP functionalized with ssDNA and a caspase-3 target peptide sequence having a fluorescent tag [114].

Table 2. PEF-based biosensors detecting cancer biomarkers.

Target analyte	Cancer type	Plasmonic structure	Biorecognition mechanism	LOD	Ref.

Exosomes in human plasma	Various types of cancer	AuNRs on Ag island film	Indirect sandwich immunoassay	0.3 ng/mL	[89]
MiRNA-210 miRNA-21	Colorectal cancer, breast cancer	Flower-like Ag NPs on cellulose fibers	DNA/miRNA hybridization	0.03 fM 0.06 fM	[108]
miRNA-21	Breast cancer	Colloidal AuNRs nanoantennas	DNA/miRNA hybridization	97.2 aM	[109]
miRNA-21	Breast cancer	AuNPs adsorbed on magnetic microparticles	RNA/RNA hybridization	9 fM	[110]
PCA3 sequence	Prostate cancer	AuNRs satellite structure	DNA/DNA hybridization	1.42 pM	[111]
CA 19-9	Pancreatic cancer	Au nanotriangular arrays on glass	Indirect sandwich immunoassay	7.7×10^{-7} U/mL	[90]
BRCA-1	Breast cancer	Colloidal AuNPs	ssDNA cleavage by CRISPR-Cas12a	0.34 fM	[112]
Caspase-3	Various types of cancer	Colloidal AuNPs	Peptide cleavage	10 pg/mL	[114]
ERBB2 gene	Breast cancer	Nanoporous Au disk	DNA/DNA hybridization (MB)	2.4 zeptomole	[86]

5.2 Infectious diseases

As summarized in Table 3, a range of biomarkers of viral and bacterial infections were detected by PEF-based biosensing platforms. PEF was used to detect IL-6 that relates to the response of the immune system to infections, a highly stable fluorescent nanoconstruct with high brightness, called 'plasmonic-fluor,' was engineered to boost the fluorescence signal strength of labels compared to a single NIR fluorophore (800CW, LI-COR) [93] (Figure 10a). This nanoconstruct has an AuNR plasmonic nanostructure for fluorescence enhancement, a polymer spacer shell, and BSA having 800CW as a light emitter and biotin as a BRE attached. AuNR/polymer was coated with BSA-800CW-biotin to be utilized as a nanoantenna. This PEF immunosorbent assay (p-FLISA) detected pro-inflammatory cytokine IL-6 with a LOD of ~ 1 fM (compared to conventional FLISA the fluorescence signal was enhanced by 4.8×10^3 -fold). Alternatively, the same sensitivity as the conventional ELISA was reached but with greatly shortened assay time (20 compared to 280 min). The same nanoconstruct was used for the development of ultra-sensitive lateral flow immunoassay (LFIA) to detect SARS-Cov-2 and IL-6 in

human plasma, SARS-Cov-2 antibody in human serum, and SARS-Cov-2 antigen nucleocapsid in nasopharyngeal (NP) swap samples [115]. In comparison to the conventional AuNP-based LFAs, an improvement in LOD by a factor of 1.8×10^3 -fold for IL-6, 5.7×10^2 -fold for the SARS-CoV-2 antibody, and 400-fold for the nucleocapsid was achieved. When the method was compared to the standard sandwich ELISA, a 30-fold increase in LOD for IL-6, a 165-fold increase for SARS-CoV-2 antibodies, and a 37-fold increase for nucleocapsid have been observed. This work demonstrates that PEF employed in lateral flow devices can also significantly improve the performance of this widely spread and established platform providing enhanced sensitivity, accuracy, and faster results compared to traditional tests.

SARS-CoV-2 was also successfully detected by amplification techniques such as thermoplasmonic-assisted cyclic cleavage for viral DNA detection. Upon binding of the target sequence on ssDNA modified Au nanoisland attached to the sensor surface, fluorophore-labeled ssDNA strands were able to bind on the free end of the target molecule, which was then cleaved by endonucleases to release the dyes and dehybridize via thermoplasmonic heating in order to produce a strong fluorescence signal. The sensor can be used for multiple cycles, achieving the LOD of 0.275 fM for the tested VTS-nsp13 sequence, and showed rapid and reliable performance also in clinical settings [98]. A point-of-care device for two genes found in SARS-CoV-2 was developed with an isothermal amplification reaction based on enzymatic recombinase amplification advanced by gold nanoarray structure. The sensor was validated with clinical samples, showing LODs of 28.3 copies/mL for the N gene and 23.3 copies/mL for the ORF1ab gene [116].

The PEF-based biosensing platforms were exploited for the diagnosis of vector-borne diseases caused by parasites including malaria, which remains one of the most life-threatening diseases in tropical countries with limited access to appropriate storage and transportation capacities. To achieve the ultrasensitive detection of a malaria biomarker *Plasmodium falciparum* lactate dehydrogenase (PfLDH), amplification substrates prepared by block copolymer micelle nanolithography (see section 3.3) were employed [66]. On top of this substrate capture antibodies were immobilized in the orientation controlled by using the photochemical immobilization technique. The capture antibody-immobilized AuNPs were exposed to PfLDH-spiked human blood and then contacted to a solution with dissolved Cy5-tagged PfLDH detection aptamer forming a sandwich (Figure 10c). The fluorescence readout signal was measured with a fluorescence microscope and an LOD of 18 fM was reported to be achieved. Another vector-borne infection with *Borrelia burgdorferi*, which is the main cause of Lyme disease, was similarly detected by a protein microarray biochip with plasmonic grating-coupled fluorescence functionality [92]. The positive and the negative control antigens were attached to gold-coated silicon microchips having a plasmonic diffraction grating (Figure 10d) and reacted with sera from patients in various stages of the disease for multiplex screening of 16 antigens. The plasmon-enhanced fluorescence signal was measured subsequent to the injection of AF647-tagged detection antibodies in the indirect sandwich assay. Considering the deposited volume of the antigens, spot size, and the molecular weight of the antibody, it was calculated that this platform can reach an analytical sensitivity of 8.5 femtomoles of IgG per spot.

Figure 10 Schematic representations of a) IL-6 detection in an indirect sandwich assay by enhancing the signal by using the plasmonic fluor (reproduced with permission from [93]), b) SARS-CoV-2 nucleocapsid antigen, and human antibodies in serum against SARS-CoV-2 spike antigen detection with LFIA using the plasmonic fluor (reproduced with permission from [115]), c) malaria biomarker PfLDH by using AuNPs synthesized by block copolymer micelle nanolithography (BCMN) in a sandwich assay having capture antibody and detection aptamer (reproduced with permission from [66]), d) human IgGs/IgMs in an indirect assay by using the grating-coupled fluorescent plasmonic technique (reproduced with permission from [117]).

Toxoplasma gondii is a protozoan parasite that causes the disease toxoplasmosis. Although it is generally asymptomatic, it can cause physical (mostly ocular) diseases and intellectual impairments (hydrocephalus) in congenitally infected children, and encephalitis in people suffering from acquired immune deficiency syndrome (AIDS) [118]. A multiplex assay platform for the serological diagnosis was aimed to detect IgG, IgA, and IgM antibodies during pregnancy [119]. An antigen mixture of *T. gondii* was immobilized on Au nanoislands by robotic array printing. Then the sensor chip was incubated with human sera or whole blood samples. For the multicolor detection, Cy3-labeled anti-human IgG, IRDye680-labeled anti-human IgM, and IRDye800-labeled anti-human IgA secondary antibodies were used for the indirect immunoassay (Figure 11a). This multiplex assay platform performed high specificity and sensitivity and required a very small amount of sample.

Human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) is mostly a sexually transmitted infection that causes AIDS leading to immune failure and remains a prominent global public health issue. For the detection of HIV DNA fragments, a label/enzyme-free approach based on catalytic hairpin assembly (CHA), as introduced in chapter 4.2, was utilized by tuning the distance between the surface of the gold triangular nanoplates (AuTNPs) and the fluorophore *N*-methyl mesoporphyrin (NMM) [120]. The sensor takes advantage of two hairpin structures, HP1 having sulfhydryl to attach AuTNPs, and HP2 which is complementary to HP1 (Figure 11b). In the case of target DNA binding, the G-quadruplex region of HP1 is available to interact with *N*-Methyl mesoporphyrin IX resulting significant fluorescence

signal increase at 645 nm. After introducing HP2, the HIV DNA is displaced to trigger further cycles of hairpin assembly causing the fluorescent signal amplification which was reported to allow for reaching LOD of 0.83 fM in human serum samples.

An advanced CHA method with DNA walkers was also implemented for the detection of RNA from the 16S ribosome of *Staphylococcus aureus*, a food-borne pathogen [102]. Colloidal gold nanoparticles were prepared and capped with a DNA hairpin structure conjugated with a fluorophore label. This fluorophore is quenched in the closed hairpin state due to the close proximity to the gold. Another DNA hairpin molecules were present in a bulk solution state and in the presence of the bacterium, which causes the surface immobilized hairpin to open the second hairpin can bind, capable of walking on the gold surface to recycle the target. Thus, cyclic reaction leads to the sequential opening of a large number of surface-attached hairpins lifting up the fluorophore labels to a distance where PEF occurs generating an output fluorescence signal. The method proved better sensitivity than other tested methods with the LOD of 8.96 fM.

Three-dimensional nanoantenna arrays were employed for PEF detection of antigens of the Ebola virus (EBOV) which causes one of the most contagious diseases with a high mortality rate [88]. Nanoantenna arrays were designed using nanopillars of silicon dioxide with gold nanoparticles attached to the sides, a gold nano-disc on the top, and perforated gold films at the bottom (Figure 11c). This structure was functionalized with a protein A/G serving as a molecular spacer optimized for sandwich immunoassay. The EBOV antigens, Fc fusion of the extracellular domain of EBOV glycoprotein (EBOVgp-Fc), and EBOV soluble glycoprotein (sGP) were detected in the indirect sandwich assay format with IRDye800-labeled secondary antibodies. The LODs of EBOVgp-Fc and sGP in human plasma by using the nanoantenna array sensing platform were found to be 5.6 pg/mL and 10.7 pg/mL, respectively, while ELISA showed notably higher LODs of 37 ng/mL for EBOVgp-Fc and 1 ng/mL for sGP.

Another severe disease with a high death rate is associated with the Avian influenza virus. Point-of-care sensor, which can rapidly detect the recombinant hemagglutinin (rHA) protein derived from the Avian influenza virus subtype H5N1 virus was developed based on PEF [95]. Silver core - SiO₂ shell colloidal nanoparticles served as substrate for the immobilization of aptamers specific to the target virus protein. Upon interaction with the target analyte, the ssDNA aptamer formed a G-quadruplex that can accommodate thiazole orange and rHA fluorophores generating an enhanced fluorescence signal. This method was reported to achieve the LOD of 3.5 ng/mL in human serum samples.

A grating-coupled fluorescence microarray technology was employed to create biomarker patterns in saliva and serum samples from pediatric patients with multisystem inflammatory syndrome (MIS-C), which is a rare but severe condition that can appear 4–6 weeks after the infection with SARS-CoV-2 [121]. These chips were fabricated in the same way described in the previously discussed study [92] and modified with capture antibodies to detect a set of 33 analytes, including cytokines, chemokines, spike protein receptors, and markers for tissue damage, cell death, and more, to characterize the biosignatures of pediatric patients with the indirect sandwich assay format (Figure 11d).

Figure 11 PEF-based biosensing platforms detecting a) human IgG, IgA, and IgM against *T. gondii* in an indirect assay by immobilizing the specific antigens on Au nanoisland surface [119], b) HIV DNA by using CHA with DNA hairpin immobilized AuTNPs (reproduced with permission from [120]), c) EBOVgp-Fc and sGP antigens of Ebola virus in an indirect sandwich assay on Au nano-discs (reproduced with permission from [88]), d) Various types of cytokines, chemokines, spike protein in an indirect sandwich immunoassay by immobilizing the specific antibodies on GC-FP Au sensors (reproduced with permission from [121]).

Table 3 PEF-based biosensors detecting biomarkers of parasitic, viral, and bacterial infections.

Target analyte	Disease	Plasmonic structure	Biorecognition mechanism	LOD	Ref.
Human antibody against spike antigen Nucleocapsid antigen	COVID-19 infection	Ag-coated AuNR plasmonic nanoantenna	Indirect sandwich immunoassay	185 pg/mL 212 pg/mL	[115]
VTS-nsp13 viral target sequence	COVID-19 infection	Gold nanoislands	DNA/DNA hybridization (amplification-based cyclic fluorescence probe cleavage)	0.275 fM	[98]
N gene ORF1ab gene	COVID-19 infection	Nanoplasmonic arrays	DNA/DNA hybridization (reverse transcription-enzymatic)	28.3 copies/mL 23.3 copies/mL	[116]

			recombinase amplification)		
Plasmodium falciparum lactate dehydrogenase	Malaria infection	AuNPs on the glass substrate	Direct sandwich assay with capture antibody and detection aptamer	18 fM	[66]
Human IgG, IgM	Lyme disease	Au-coated silicon microchip	Indirect immunoassay	Not specified	[92]
Human IgG, IgA IgM	<i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> infection	Au nanoislands	Indirect immunoassay	Not specified	[119]
HIV DNA	AIDS	AuTNPs	DNA/DNA hybridization (CHA)	0.83 fM	[120]
16S rRNA	Staphylococcal food-borne disease	AuNPs	DNA/DNA hybridization (CHA)	8.96 fM	[102]
EBOVgp-Fc sGP	Ebola virus disease	Au nanoantenna array on a glass substrate	Indirect sandwich immunoassay	5.6 pg/mL 10.7 pg/mL	[88]
rHA	Avian influenza	Core-shell Ag-NP	Aptamer for G-quadruplex	3.5 ng/mL	[95]

5.3 Other clinical applications

Additional studies explored the implementation of PEF for the analysis of analytes related to other health conditions including cardiovascular and neurological disorders and organ injury as wrapped up in Table 4. Cardiovascular diseases are one of the most common causes of death globally. Shortly after a heart attack, even if it is without any symptoms, it is possible to detect cardiac troponin I (cTnI) biomarker in the blood as it enters the bloodstream quickly and stays circulating for a couple of days. This analyte was detected by PEF direct sandwich immunoassay with Alexa Fluor 647-labeled detection antibody [122]. ATR in the Kretschmann configuration was used with a light pipe configuration and Fresnel lens - improved collection efficiency of fluorescence light. The capture antibody was immobilized via the protein G fused to ORLA85 protein and an LOD of 0.98 ng/mL was reported. This sensor was less sensitive than ELISA with an LOD of 0.21 ng/mL, however, due to the pH-tolerant ORLA85, the semi-continuous measurement was possible. In another study, a similar optical configuration was used for cTnI assay with PEF readout, where detection antibody was conjugated to Alexa Fluor 647 in order to specifically recognize the cTnI [72]. Assay performance was investigated for direct, sandwich, and competitive formats with polyclonal and monoclonal antibodies. For the

competitive assay, the detection antibody was preincubated with a liquid sample before flowing the solution over the sensor surface with immobilized cTnI protein by amine coupling. In this study, an LOD of 19 pM was achieved for a detection time of 45 min.

Traumatic brain injury (TBI) is a common neurological disorder, which can lead to neurodegeneration. Nanosphere lithography was used to construct an Au nanopyramid array pattern on glass to serve as PEF substrate with a thin layer of silica reducing fluorescence quenching and immobilized capture antibody specific TBI biomarker - glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP) [123]. In sandwich immunoassay format, detection antibody labeled with NIR fluorophore Dylight 755 was used yielding plasmonic biosensor detecting GFAP with LOD of 0.6 pg/mL that was improved with respect to ELISA providing LOD of 9.8 pg/mL.

PEF was also employed in assays where metallic nanostructures serve as labels in micro-array- based detection platforms [124]. The dendron-modified glass substrate was utilized to immobilize the probe DNA to capture miRNA-134 which is a brain-specific biomarker responsible for neurogenesis/synaptic development and has been demonstrated in previous studies to be associated with diseases such as epilepsy, major depressive disorder (MDD), Alzheimer's disease and frontotemporal dementia [125], [126], [127]. Fluorescence-amplifying nanocuboids (FANCs) with precisely controlled PEF were developed by using gold nanorods conjugated with Alexa Fluor 647 via ssDNA linkers and by using an Ag shell. The DNA/miRNA hybrid on the microarray was recognized by a monoclonal antibody reacted with a FANC-tagged secondary antibody (Figure 12a). A 100-fold higher sensitivity compared to the commercial fluorescence labels was achieved providing a dynamic range from 100 aM to 1 pM.

An alternative approach to amplify fluorescence readout signal was explored based on contacting fluorophore labels captured on the sensor surface after performing an assay with metallic nanostructures tethered to a flexible polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) sheet (Figure 12b) [59]. This element was referred as to a plasmonic patch, and it was used for multiplexed detection of multiple biological targets. By this approach, LOD for the kidney injury molecule-1 (KIM1) which is an early-stage biomarker of acute kidney injury (AKI) was ~30 times lower (0.5 pg/mL) than that of ELISA (15.6 pg/mL), and comparing to the unenhanced signal, 36-fold fluorescence enhancement in the plasmonic patch was measured.

Exosome biomarkers carrying miRNA cargo were analyzed with the help of PEF for non-destructive characterizing stem cell neurogenesis [85]. The platform combined selective isolation of exosomes and sensitive miRNA detection by multifunctional magneto-plasmonic nanorod prepared via an anodized aluminum oxide template. These magneto-plasmonic nanostructures were composed of Ni segments conjugated with IgG antibody specific to a membrane marker CD63, and Au plasmonic segment with a fluorophore (5(6)-carboxyfluorescein (FAM))-labeled ssDNA hairpin (Figure 12c). The antibodies were used for the capturing of exosomes and their subsequent isolation by applied magnetic field gradient. After the exosome lysis, released miRNA cargo was detected by the same structure by reacting with the ssDNA hairpin that changed its conformation, and the conjugated fluorophore was switched from quenched to PEF-amplified state. The method was successfully applied to detect neuronal biomarker miRNA-124 in human induced pluripotent stem cell-derived neural stem cells (hiPSC-NSCs) with good linearity ($R^2 = 0.98$) at a wide range of concentrations (ranging from 1 pM to 1 μ M). With this multifunctional magneto-plasmonic -based approach it is envisaged to be possible monitoring stem cell differentiation in time for future stem cell therapies. Additionally, with this technique it can be possible to detect the exosomes as the sources of early-stage cancer biomarkers, this technique can be used for advanced diagnosis.

An important byproduct of DNA synthesis is pyrophosphate (PPi), which serves as a target analyte in sensors or for sequencing methods. It was used in PEF sensors for monitoring point mutations, which

can be the cause of various genetic diseases. For this purpose, the RCA method, an enzymatic amplification technique (introduced in chapter 4.3), was used to detect the point mutation in the DNA sequence, producing PPI in the process. The detection was employed on the surface of core-shell nanocube particles modified with fluorophores with a turn-on and off mechanism based on the high affinity between the byproduct PPI and copper-ions, achieving the LOD of 1.3 pM [128]. The same mechanism was exploited with nanobipyramids based on LSP fluorescence enhancement of near-infrared dyes, providing a stronger signal than compared to gold nanorods, where the fluorescence quenching is induced by copper-ions for bio-applications with the LOD of 80 nM [129].

Figure 12 Schematic illustrations of the PEF-based biosensors detecting a) miRNA-134 with DNA/miRNA hybridization with FANC-tagged secondary antibody on a dendron-modified glass substrate (reproduced with permission from [124]), b) KIM-1 by using plasmonic patch integrated on the assay surface having fluorescent dye (Reproduced with permission from [59]), c) miRNA-124 with DNA/miRNA hybridization by using Au/Ni NRs [85].

Table 4 Overview of PEF-based biosensors detecting biomarkers related to organ injury, inflammation, and neurodegenerative diseases.

Target analyte	Disease	Plasmonic structure	Biorecognition mechanism	LOD	Ref.
Cardiac troponin I	Heart attack	Flat Au film	Direct sandwich immunoassay	0.98 ng/mL	[122]
Cardiac troponin I	Heart attack	Flat Au film	Competitive immunoassay	19 pM	[72]
Glial fibrillary acidic protein	Traumatic brain injury (TBI)	Au nanopyramids on glass	Direct sandwich immunoassay	0.6 pg/mL	[123]
miRNA-134	Neurogenesis-related	AuNRs	DNA/miRNA hybrid detection by indirect immunoassay	1 fM	[124]

KIM-1	Kidney injury	AuNRs on PDMS film	Direct sandwich immunoassay	0.5 pg/mL	[59]
miRNA-124	Stem cell neurogenesis	Au/Ni NRs	DNA/miRNA hybridization	Not specified	[85]
Caspase-3	Neurodegenerative disease	Colloidal AuNPs	Peptide cleavage	10 pg/mL	[114]
Interleukin 6	Inflammation, lethal sepsis	Ag-coated AuNR nanoantenna	Direct sandwich assay	362 pg/mL	[115]
Interleukin 6	Inflammation, lethal sepsis	Ag-coated AuNR nanoantenna	Direct sandwich assay	1 fM	[93]
Pyrophosphate	Various genetic diseases	Core-shell Au nanocube	RCA	1.3 pM	[128]
Pyrophosphate	Various genetic diseases	Au nanobipyramid antennas	RCA	80 nM	[129]

6. Applications in environmental monitoring

Environmental contamination poses a significant threat to the human population and nature vulnerable to various pollutants. Their major part originates from human activities and enters into the environment through pathways like industrial effluents, biomedical waste, gas emissions, and agricultural chemicals. The further discussion centers around the advances of PEF-based sensors and biosensors for the monitoring pollutants providing information on the analytical performance in comparison to limits set by the regulatory bodies. The below discussion also highlights the different sensing materials like polymers, 2D materials like graphene, mesoporous materials and metal organic frameworks employed for the detection of water pollutants. An overview of targeted analytes is arranged along the lines of heavy metal ion pollution in water, detection of pesticides in water and soil, and the analysis of pharmaceutical residues in water and food-derived matrices.

6.1 Heavy metal ions

Industrial effluents, containing substances like dyes, surfactants, minerals, and toxic heavy metals, endanger aquatic life and ecosystems. Release of these effluents introduces harmful metals such as chromium, copper, lead, iron, manganese, cadmium, mercury, nickel, and zinc into water bodies that can leach e.g. to potable water sources. Regulatory bodies such as the World Health Organization (WHO), the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), and the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) set concentration limits for these pollutants, considering exceeding these limits as hazardous for living organisms [130]. For instance, WHO's permissible limits for heavy metal ions in drinking water include 0.05 ppm for Arsenic (As-III/V), Lead (Pb-II), and 0.005 ppm for Cadmium (Cd-II), Chromium (Cr-VI/III), 0.001 ppm for Mercury (Hg), and 1.5 ppm for Copper (Cu-II). In comparison, the US EPA has established limits of 0.01 ppm, 0.015 ppm, 0.005 ppm, 0.05 ppm, 0.002 ppm, and 1.3 ppm for the same pollutants

[131]. As shown by further discussed examples and overview in Table 5, recent progress in mostly colloidal metallic nanoparticle – based system provides routes to detect these analytes with the required sensitivity.

Optical sensors, particularly fluorescent ones, have been proven as valuable analytical tools providing high specificity, low detection limits, rapid response, and simplicity for the analysis of heavy metals. A polyacrylonitrile (PAN)/noble metal/SiO₂ nanofibrous mat mixed with conjugated polyelectrolytes (CPE) was developed as a photonic crystal-enhanced fluorescence (PEF) substrate [132]. As illustrated in (Figure 13 a), the sensor utilized poly-(p-phenyleneethynylene) with hydrophilic sulfonate groups (PPESO₃OR) quenched by heavy metal ions through metal ions-induced aggregation. The sensor, especially effective for Pb²⁺ than other heavy metal ions (Figure 13b) achieved a detection limit of 17 picomolar (Cd²⁺, Mn²⁺). The same group designed a PEF sensor using fluorescence isothiocyanate (FITC)/Au₁Ag₄@SiO₂ for Fe³⁺ detection, reaching a 20 nM detection limit [133]. Embedding fluorescent materials with plasmonic materials enhanced fluorescence intensity in both studies.

Figure 13 a) A diagram depicting the fabrication process of PAN/Ag/SiO₂ nanofibers and the detection of metal ions through enhanced fluorescence and subsequent amplified fluorescence quenching, b) fluorescence graph with and without nanofiber. Reproduced with permission from [132].

In another approach, heavy metal ions were detected utilizing colloidal polyvinyl pyrrolidone (PVP) capped gold nanoparticles (PVP-Au NPs). These fluorescent PVP-Au NPs exhibited a selective interaction with Hg²⁺ ions, in comparison to other metal ions. By monitoring the Hg²⁺-induced quenching PVP fluorescence signal, LOD for Hg²⁺ was determined to be 100 nM [134]. The same research group also developed a sensor array using three different copper nanoclusters (CuNCs) combined with polyethyleneimine (PEI), histidine (His), and Glutathione (GSH) to detect 12 metal ions (Pb²⁺, Fe³⁺, Cu²⁺, Cd²⁺, Cr³⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Zn²⁺, Ag⁺, Fe²⁺, Hg²⁺, and Al³⁺). The corresponding LODs for these ions are provided in the linked Table 2. Water-soluble photosynthetic antenna protein Peridinin-chlorophyll-protein (PCP) complexes were reported for the analysis of Hg²⁺ with the use of Au microplates [135]. This approach relied on oxidative-reductive reactions and specific binding interactions with Hg²⁺. The sensor exhibited a gradual increase in the intensity of the characteristic fluorescence peak at a wavelength of 673 nm with rising concentrations of Hg²⁺. The obtained relationship displayed a linear detection range up to a concentration of 42 μM, with an LOD of 0.75 nM. A recent study introduced a sensor for detecting Pb²⁺ ions using graphene quantum dots (GQDs) and AuNP quenching that was modulated by selective interaction with DNAzyme stands [136]. The sensor utilized a colloidal solution of complexed GQDs and AuNPs via catalytic and complementary DNA strands. Pb²⁺ ions for quantitative measurement of fluorescence recovery upon interaction with Pb²⁺ ions. The device

demonstrated a detection range of 50 nM to 4 μM for Pb^{2+} ions, with an LOD of 16.7 nM. Other researchers have introduced periodic mesoporous organosilicas (PMOS) designed specifically for detecting Cu^{2+} ions. This composite features a multilayer core-shell structure comprising colloidal Ag-nanocubes capped with PMO [137]. Its design involves the synthesis of Ag nanocubes, deposition of a silica spacer shell, and construction of outer periodic mesoporous organosilicas. Upon interaction with Cu^{2+} ions, noticeable changes in fluorescence spectrum occur due to ring-opening mechanisms triggered by complexation inside the bis (rhodamine Schiff-base derivative) groups allowing detection of Cu^{2+} with LOD of 0.3 μM . Other investigations have reported similar studies with the utilization of Au_{25} -absorbed $\text{Ag}@\text{SiO}_2$ core-shell nanoparticles for the detection of Cu^{2+} ions [138].

Moreover, a fluorescence sensor array employing a single probe to distinguish heavy metal ion fingerprints. They chemically reduced HAuCl_4 with 2-mercapto-1-methylimidazole (MMI) and polyvinylpyrrolidone, producing fluorescent gold nanoclusters (AuNCs). The fluorescence emission of PVP/MMI-AuNC was pH-dependent, shifting from yellow ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 512 \text{ nm}$) to red ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 700 \text{ nm}$) at pH 12.0 and 6.0, respectively. When exposed to metal ions, PVP/MMI-AuNC exhibited distinct signals at 512 nm and 700 nm. This single probe successfully identified and differentiated seven heavy metal ions (Ag^+ , Fe^{3+} , Fe^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Sn^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , and Hg^{2+}), detecting concentrations as low as 17 nM (Ag^+), below the EPA's drinking water limit [139]. There are several other approaches utilized to prepare the PEF-based sensor to detect the heavy metal ions below the acceptable ranges. A combined colorimetric and fluorescence sensor concept based on rhodamine 6G thioamide was utilized [140], where the fluorescence signal was enhanced by AgNPs. The sensor showed improved Hg^{2+} LOD of 0.030 ppb (with silver nanoparticles) compared to 49 ppb (only with rhodamine 6G thioamide). A multichannel optical fluorescence sensor utilizing microtiter well plates with gold nanoparticle clusters and fluorescence probes including colloidal N-doped carbon dots (NCDs) was developed for heavy metal analysis [141]. Metal ions were detected in both tap water and soil extracts with the LOD for Cd^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , and Hg^{2+} determined to be 0.15, 0.20, and 0.09 μM , respectively. The metal-organic framework (MOF) NH_2 -UiO66 was functionalized with carbon dots and AuNPs for the detection of Pb^{2+} (Figure 14a). A FRET mechanism was observed between the fluorescent HS-C layer and AuNPs on the UiO-66 surface within HS-C/Au/(x)/UiO-66 particles (Figure 14b). The sensor achieved a LOD of 0.1 ppb for Pb^{2+} [142].

Figure 14 a) Diagram outlining the creation process of HS-C/Au(x)/UiO-66, involving thiolation followed by preformed AuNP deposition on UiO-66 crystals in the first step. In step 2, in-situ carbon dot synthesis takes place, followed by thiolation in the final step, b) FRET process that occurs between the fluorescent HS-C Layer and the AuNPs on the UiO-66 surface within HS-C/Au(x)/UiO-66 particles. Reproduced with permission from [142].

Table 5 Overview of PEF-based techniques developed for the analysis of heavy metal ions.

Target analyte	Analyte sensitive material and PEF structure	LOD / WHO limit	Detection range	Ref.
Pb^{2+}	PAN/Ag/SiO ₂ nanofibrous mat with CPE solution	17 pM (0.003 ppb)/0.05 ppm	0 to 3.0 μ M	[132]
Hg^{2+}	Aptamer-Ag@SiO ₂ NPs	0.33 nM (0.066 ppb)/0.001 ppm	0 to 900 nM	[143]
Hg^{2+}	PCP conjugated with Au microplates	0.75 nM (0.150 ppb)/0.05 ppm	0 to 20 μ M	[135]
Hg^{2+}	Au nanocluster-modified paper substrate	1.2 nM (0.240 ppb)/0.001ppm	0 to 1000 nM	[144]

Pb ²⁺	GQDs/AuNPs	16.7 nM (3.460 ppb) /0.05 ppm	50 nM to 4 μM	[136]
Ag ⁺	PVP/MMI-AuNC	17 nM/0.1 ppm	0 to 50 μM	[139]
Fe ³⁺	FITC/Au ₁ Ag ₄ @SiO ₂	20 nM/3 ppm	0 to 63 μM	[133]
Hg ²⁺	Pyridoxal conjugated BSA-AuNCs	31.9 nM (6.39 ppb)/0.05 ppm	99 to 1750 mM	[145]
Cu ²⁺	Peptide-AuNCs	52 nmol/L/1.5 ppm	0 to 4.2 μM	[146]
Hg ²⁺	PVP-Au	100 nM (20.04 ppb)/0.05 ppm	0 to 60 μM	[134]
Pb ²⁺ , Cu ²⁺ , Cd ²⁺ , Co ²⁺ , Ni ²⁺ , Zn ²⁺	CuNCs with PEI, His, GSH	0.615 μM (0.127 ppb)/0.05 ppm 0.107 μM, (6.799 ppb)/1.5 ppm 0.650 μM, (20.04ppb)/0.005 ppm 0.322 μM (18.95 ppb),/0.01 ppm 0.265 μM (15.55 ppb), 0.07 ppm 0.827 μM (54.06 ppb)/5 ppm	1.5 μM to 800 μM	[147]
Cd ²⁺ , Pb ²⁺ , Hg ²⁺	AuNCs@NCDs	0.15 μmol/L, (18.04 ppb)/0.005 ppm 0.20 μmol/L, (41.44 ppb)/0.05 ppm 0.09 μmol/L (10.11 ppb)/0.05 ppm	0-75 μmol/L, 0-75 μmol/L, 0-45 μmol/L	[141]
Cu ²⁺	Ag nanocube@SiO ₂ @PMOs	0.3 μM (19.063 ppb)/1.5 ppm	1 to 5 μM	[137]
Pb ²⁺	HS-C/Au (1.4) UiO-66	8 ppt/0.05 ppm	0 – 10 ppb	[142]

Hg ²⁺	Hexagonal mesoporous silica (HMS-Ag-R)	0.9 ppb/0.001ppm	10 to 110 ppb	[148]
Hg ²⁺	Rhodamine derivatives grafted AuNS@Ag core-shell nanocubes (CSN)	0.94 ppb/0.001 ppm	0.001 to 1000 ppm	[149]
Hg ²⁺	HMS-Ag-R-2SH	2.1 ppb/0.001 ppm	0 to 10 ppm	[150]

6.2 Pesticides

Pesticides, while effective against agricultural pests, heavily pollute the environment, contaminating water, soil, air, and food sources. Pesticides residues harm non-target species including the human population, raising concerns about ecosystems and the safety of food and water resources. Pesticides in water sources can lead to severe health issues in humans, including respiratory problems and cancer, making regular monitoring essential to ensure safe drinking water. Environmental ecosystems are also at risk, as pesticides disrupt aquatic life and damage biodiversity, impacting the delicate balance of ecosystems. Furthermore, contaminated water used in agriculture jeopardizes crop yields, leading to economic losses for farmers. By detecting pesticides in water, timely interventions can be implemented to safeguard public health, preserve ecosystems, and sustain agriculture, highlighting the critical importance of monitoring and addressing pesticide contamination in water sources. In order to monitor the presence of these compounds, established analytical techniques like gas chromatography and liquid chromatography with mass spectrometry represent the currently used gold standard methods. However, they typically rely on bulky instruments that need to be deployed in specialized laboratories and require operation with highly trained personnel. In order to simplify the analysis and allow for more frequent on-site tests without the need of transporting the analyzed samples to central laboratories, fluorescent sensors, and biosensors have emerged as a cost-effective, efficient, and rapid solution for direct pesticide detection. PEF-based sensors and biosensors offer a route to enhance sensitivity for detecting pesticides in order to fulfil limits stipulated by regulatory bodies. For instance, the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency set permissible limits for pesticides such as glyphosate at 0.7 ppm and paraquat at 0.03 mg/L. In below sections, the selection of work reporting on PEF-based methodologies pursued for the detection of compounds relevant to environmental monitoring applications is presented with an overview of analytes included in Table 6.

Carbon quantum dots were employed for the detection of carbaryl pesticides by quenching their fluorescence signal with AuNPs. Acetylcholinesterase hydrolyzes acetylcholine to thiocholine, which aggregates AuNPs and thus modulates carbon quantum dot fluorescence emission. The herbicide carbaryl reduces the effect of thiocholine, preventing Au nanoparticle agglomeration leading to carbon quantum dot fluorescence recovery. The detection range for carbaryl content of 0.20-150 µg/L was reported with an LOD of 0.06 µg/L [151]. Organophosphorous (OP) chemicals dominate pesticides and germicides used in agriculture. Even at modest doses, OP substances are toxic to humans. The construction of a fluorescent instrument with high selectivity and sensitivity was accomplished using straightforward techniques. Silver/gold bimetallic nanoparticles modified with Rhodamine B (RB) were utilized. The fluorescence of RB-Ag/AuNPs was diminished until they were exposed to OP pesticides. Due to the stronger cooperation between Ag/AuNPs and OPs than with RB, RB fluorescence recovers as the molecule departs Ag/AuNPs. The LOD for OPs in fruit and water samples was od 1.8 pg/mL [152].

Metal-organic frameworks (MOF) are frequently combined with gold nanoclusters (AuNC) for PEF sensors. Integration of MOFs with AuNC was, for instance, employed in the aggregation-induced emission (AIE) detection principle of OPs based on quenching of enzymolysis by acetylcholinesterase and choline oxidase. This approach was reported for on-site quantitative OP detection with an LOD of 0.4 g/L [153]. Dimethoate, an organophosphorus insecticide and acaricide, is widely used to control pests that damage crops, fruits, vegetables, and ornamentals. Long-term or excessive exposure to dimethoate can cause nausea, vomiting, headache, disorientation, and muscular twitching. A highly sensitive dimethoate probe was reported by utilizing competitive binding with Rhodamine B and quenching by the presence of AuNPs [154]. This method allows for highly sensitive detection of dimethoate with an LOD of 0.004 ppm.

In addition to OP, acetamiprid (ACE) was detected by a modulating quenching of fluorescence signal from ssDNA aptamer conjugated with Cy3-label. This aptamer was hybridized with short ssDNA oligo attached to AuNPs and upon specific capture ACE assisted it dissociated from the metal surface, resulting in a concentration-dependent increase in fluorescence intensity (Figure 15a). This readout was combined with colorimetric LSPR detection with excellent sensitivity and specificity for ACE and OPs, detecting ACE at 166.7 pg mL⁻¹ and OPs at 0.17 fg mL⁻¹ (Figure 15b) [155].

Figure 15 a) Illustrative diagram depicting a dual-readout sensor utilizing fluorescence and LSPR for the detection of ACE and OPs. b) Sensor parameters fluorescence spectral response, regression plot, selectivity plot, Fluorescence image of sensor system. Reproduced with permission from [155].

Table 6 Overview of PEF sensors and biosensors targeting pesticides.

Target analyte	Plasmonic structure	LOD	Detection range	Ref.
Glyphosate	GSH-Au NCS @ZIF8	0.28 nM	0 to 100 nM	[156]
2-aminoanthracene	Ag@SiO ₂	1 nM	1 nM to 800 nM	[157]

Paraquate	GSH/ β -CDs-AuNCs	1.2 ng/mL	5.0-350 ng/mL	[158]
Carbendazim	AuNPs/Rhodamine B	2.33 nM	2.33 to 800 nM	[159]
Thiram	AuNP decorated QD embedded nanobead	7 nM	2 μ M	[160]
Acetamiprid, organophosphorus pesticides	DNA-AuNPs	1.667 pg/mL, 0.17 fg/mL	0 – 150 ng/mL	[155]
Organophosphorus pesticide	RB-Ag/Au	0.0018 ng/mL	0.0033-0.28 ng/mL	[152]
Parathion-methyl, fenitrothion, fenthion	TMB ²⁺ -mediated AuNRs	2.42 ng/ml 0.95 ng/ml 6.52 ng/ml	0.04 to 5.00 μ g/ml 0.01 to 5.00 μ g/ml 0.01 to 5.00 μ g/ml	[161]
Carabaryl	B,N -doped CQDs	0.006 μ g/L	0.20-150 μ g/L	[151]
Acephate	AuNC@ZIF-8	0.4 μ g/L	0.001 – 100 mg/L	[153]
Paraoxan	OPH-pyranine derivative with si-coated AgNPs	1 ppb	1 – 100 ng/mL	[162]
Diazionon, iprobenfos, edifenphos	AuNPs with imidazole	53.3 ppb, 53.6 ppb, 27.9 ppb	10 ppb- 1 ppm	[163]

Chlorpyrifos, profenofos	CD-GO	0.14 ppb, 2.05 ppb	1 ppm	[164]
Ethion, parathion, malathion, fenthion	Ag-Au NP bimetallic	228 ppm, 231 ppm, 1189 ppm, 1835 ppm	1.66 to 6.62 x 10 ⁻⁵ M	[165]
Dimethoate	RB-AuNPs	0.004 ppm	0.005- 1.0 ppm	[154]
Thiram, carbaryl, paraquat, fipronil	Silver nanowire 3D random crossed-wire woodpile (3D-RCW)	50 μM, 5 μM, 20 μM	~0 to 100 nM	[166]
Parathion, triazophos, chlorpyrifos	Au @pt nanozyme	9.88 ng/kg 3.91 ng/kg 1.47 ng/kg	10 to 150 μg/kg	[167]
Dichlorvos, trichlorfon, paraoxon	IDA+ AuNP	0.03 mg/kg, 0.009 mg/kg, 0.007 mg/kg	0.25 to 4 mg/kg	[168]

6.3 Pharmaceutical residues

The widespread use of antimicrobial substances like antibiotics leads to the infiltration of aquatic ecosystems. The introduction of antibiotic medications and pharmaceutical goods into water ecosystems can occur through multiple pathways. As individuals consume antibiotics or other pharmacological chemicals, their systems undergo metabolic processes, resulting in the excretion of both unaltered and partially modified molecules through urine and feces. Pharmaceutical chemicals have the potential to infiltrate wastewater systems via sewage treatment plants. Certain persons may choose to discard outdated or undesirable medications by means of direct flushing to wastewater. The act of directly disposing of pharmaceutical compounds can result in the introduction to the environment where these substances can interfere with the behavior, growth, and reproductive processes of aquatic species. Furthermore, antibiotics, crucial for managing infections, contribute to bacterial resistance, posing unpredictable threats to human health. Traditional wastewater treatment methods struggle to degrade antibiotics effectively, exacerbating environmental issues. Monitoring antibiotics in water sources is critical, necessitating their precise identification and evaluation.

Antibiotic residues like streptomycin were detected using colloidal AuNPs with DNA aptamer hairpin. The assay was designed based on fluorescence quenching. It showed excellent selectivity toward streptomycin and sensing in milk samples was tested with LOD of 47.6 nM [169]. Other than water residues, antibiotics in milk were detected using a novel ratiometric fluorescent probe that utilizes the simultaneous integration of AuNCs and green emitting carbon dots (gCDs) into ZIF-8 for the purpose of analysing Cephalexin (CFX). The sensor demonstrates dual emissions at 520 and 630 nm when subjected to a single excitation wavelength of 400 nm. The fluorescence emission of AuNCs at a wavelength of 630 nm is specifically suppressed by the presence of CFX, while the fluorescence emission of graphene quantum dots (gCDs) at a wavelength of 520 nm remains relatively unaffected. The fluorescence signal ratio (F_{520}/F_{630}) of the composite (gCDc/AuNCs @ ZIF-8) exhibits a linear relationship with the concentration of CFX within the range of 0.1 to 6 ng/mL with a LOD of 0.04 ng/mL, which falls below the maximum residues limit (MRL) of 100 ng/mL established by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) [170]. Besides antibiotic residues, the PEF method was also used to find dangerous residues like picric acid (PA). For example, poly(allylamine) hydrochloride (PAH)-capped AuNPs were used for detecting PA in water. While PAH is deposited on the surface of Au-SiO₂ core-shell nanoparticles, the PAH fluorescence grows significantly brighter. The distance between the gold core and PAH is controlled by the silica shell. When PAH is mixed with gold nanoparticles with a width of about 45 nm, the increase is almost 280 times. In the linear range, it is thought that 79 nM is the most that the sensor can measure [171].

The example shown in Figure 16a describes the implementation of a streptomycin biosensor relying on core-shell Au-Pd nanoparticles acting as a quencher and adsorbed fluorescent ssDNA aptamer with silver nanoclusters (DNA-AgNCs). The addition of G nucleotides to the ssDNA hairpin loop resulted in an enhancement of the fluorescence intensity of the DNA-AgNCs (Figure 16b). Au-Pd nanoparticles exhibited enhanced quenching capabilities in the extended wavelength region, while also considerably broadening the UV absorption spectrum. When interacting with the target analyte, the aptamer detached from the quenched Au-Pd nanoparticles associated with increased emitted fluorescence intensity. The sensor exhibited a detection range for streptomycin of 50-1250 nM, with a limit of detection of 18.7 nM [172].

Figure 16 a) Mechanism of the proposed fluorescent sensor based on hairpin DNA-AgNCs and Au@PdNPs for STR detection. b) Normalized fluorescence intensities of DNA3-AgNCs with Au@PdNPs at different concentrations. c) Specific detection of the STR and other antibiotics. d) Relative fluorescence intensities of DNA3-AgNCs with Au@PdNPs at different concentrations (reproduced with permission from [172]).

Table 7 Comparison of PEF sensors and biosensors developed for pharmaceutical residues.

Target analyte	Plasmonic nanostructure	LOD	Detection range	Ref.
Ciprofloxacin, enrofloxacin, lomefloxacin	AgNP	90 ng L ⁻¹	0.025 to 1.0 mg L ⁻¹	[173]
		5 ng L ⁻¹	5.0 to 160 ng L ⁻¹	
		6 ng L ⁻¹	0.01 to 0.8 mg L ⁻¹	
Ciprofloxacin	Al ³⁺ and (AuNCs) templated with glutathione	1.4 nM	0 to 120 μM	[174]

Danofloxacin	Aluminum (III)	0.9 ng mL ⁻¹	3– 100 ng mL ⁻¹	[175]
Danofloxacin Ciprofloxacin Norfloxacin	AuNP	5.0 x10 ⁻⁸ M 9.6 x10 ⁻⁸ M 13.3 x10 ⁻⁸ M	1.0 x 10 ⁻⁷ - 7.5 x 10 ⁻⁶ M 3.0 x 10 ⁻⁷ - 7.5 x 10 ⁻⁶ M 9.0 x 10 ⁻⁷ – 1.0 x 10 ⁻⁵ M	[176]
Ciprofloxacin	Isomeric In(III)-MOFs, BUT-172 and BUT-173	50 ppb	0 to 300 μL	[177]
Kanamycin	bovine serum albumin stabilized gold nanoclusters (BSA-AuNCs)	0.032 nM	0.04 – 7.0 nM	[178]
Kanamycin	Aptasensor based on Exo III, and AuNPs	321 pM	0 – 100 nM	[179]

7. Single-molecule analysis

Fluorescence measurements take advantage of established optical instrumentations enabling the detection of optical signal even from individual fluorescence emitters and they routinely support analytical techniques operating at single molecule level. In conjunction with spatially confined optical probing in small metallic cavities referred as to zero-mode waveguides (ZMW), such capability paved the way to important technologies for sequencing nucleic acid-based molecules. It serves for the monitoring of the reaction of individual ssDNA chain fragments with fluorophore-labelled nucleotides diffusing into the cavity [180]. The spatially confined optical probing allows to efficiently block background signal originating from the molecules in bulk solution and allows for reading of nucleotide sequence assembling upon the formation of dsDNA strand. In addition, ZMW is increasingly used also for biomolecular interaction studies of fluorophore-labelled molecules at concentrations relevant to biological conditions. The development of techniques capable of observing biomolecular interactions at single molecule level (and not necessarily at low concentrations) [181] is gaining momentum in order to explore new phenomena that stay hidden from conventional techniques relying on the probing of molecular ensembles.

ZMW are typically prepared in the form of nanoholes with a diameter ranging from 50 to 200 nm in a 100 nm thick aluminum layer forming a volume in aL to zL that is substantially below fL volumes achievable by diffraction-limited focal volume of optical microscopes. They are typically designed for operating in broad wavelength range and their plasmonic properties are not exploited. However, by engineering the geometry of the nanoapertures (circular, rectangular, elliptical) and using other types of metals such as gold or silver, plasmonic manipulation with fluorophore emitters can be introduced. In particular, the PEF in such ZMW cavities was proposed for improved time resolution for fast biomolecular dynamics [182]. Moreover, a possible combination of nanopore-based sequencing based on electronic readout with optical detection was explored by integrating nanopore structures with plasmonic metallic apertures [183]. Besides PEF, other spectroscopy tools such as surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy were proposed [184] and the possibility of exploiting phenomena including local molecular trapping and plasmonic heating was discussed [185].

A new generation of PEF biosensors capable of monitoring individual affinity binding events is emerging based on DNA origami structures (which can be designed to self-assemble in controlled 2D and 3D geometries, see Chapter 2.2) [186]. Constructs with predefined functionalization locations can be used to precisely place BREs to plasmonic hotspots at distances from metallic nanoparticles that allow avoiding quenching and ensure maximum enhancement [60], [187]. Functionalized DNA origami plasmonic nanoantennas were demonstrated for single fluorophore measurements with $EF > 400$ [187] and were also implemented for the detection of biomolecules. It was demonstrated to readout affinity binding of individual ssDNA and ssRNA sequences specific for Zika virus in buffer and in biologically relevant sample by using direct MB-based assay [188], [62]. In addition, detection of one single antibody recognizing digoxigenin in conjunction with a nanoswitch placed in the hotspots was reported [189]. Upon binding of the anti-digoxigenin, the nanoswitch opens up and the quencher can no longer act on the fluorophore due to the spatial distance, which will emit the detectable signal.

8. Conclusions

Since initial investigations of the coupling between fluorescent emitters and surface plasmon resonances on metallic nanostructure demonstrated the ability to efficiently amplify fluorescence signal, we witness flourishing amounts of its applications in analytical technologies for the analysis of chemical and biological compounds. Within the last decade, the field of plasmon-enhanced fluorescence – PEF – benefited from improved routes for the preparation of metallic nanostructures with well-controlled plasmonic characteristics. Besides the fabrication precision, efforts were devoted to the development of protocols that allow for cost-efficient preparation of the structures suitable for disposable use. Even without complex lithography preparation routes extraordinarily high fluorescence enhancement factors $EF > 10^3$ were reported, which is essential for the utilization in highly sensitive practical analytical tests. In conjunction with the advancements in biointerfaces and assay formats powered by amplification means such as enzymatic rolling circle amplification or catalytic hairpin assembly, the combination with PEF paved the way for ultrasensitive analysis of nucleic acid as well as protein-based analytes. The PEF assays were implemented by the use of established laboratory equipment such as fluorescence microarray or microtiter plate readers and allowed reaching LODs below fM concentrations in complex biological fluids. This performance is comparable to the gold standard tools including digital polymerase chain reaction (dPCR) or digital ELISA techniques used for high sensitivity analysis of nucleic acids and proteins. In particular in the field of biomarkers analysis and detection of harmful species relevant to medical diagnostics, the PEF sensitivity in conjunction with simplified detection format holds the potential to establish this method in the field of expanding the medical molecular diagnostics market. Environmental monitoring represents another field that

was particularly addressed by PEF sensors and biosensors. These efforts aim to deliver simplified yet sufficiently sensitive detection schemes in order to allow for on-site analysis that is currently not possible to realize with standardly used mass spectrometry – based techniques. Moreover, PEF is increasingly used in emerging research branch devoted to single-molecule detection and single-molecule interaction analysis, most commonly by the use of dedicated instruments or high-end fluorescence microscopes. However, efforts to improve the availability of such studies by affordable optics, where the limited performance is compensated by the PEF – based amplification, are pursued and hold potential for future exploration and grow of this vibrant research and technology field.

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